

The Effect of Work Integrated Learning System on Employee Performance at Pt Kerabatani Indonesia

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the effect of the work-integrated learning system on employee performance at PT KerabaTani Indonesia. The population in this study are all employees recruited by PT KerabaTani Indonesia in the July 2022 period, totaling 40 people. The sample in this study uses a census scheme, namely a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples. The data processing technique in this study uses Partial Least Square with the help of SmartPLS software. The results of this study are that the work-integrated learning system has a significant effect on employee performance and work-integrated learning training can mediate the relationship between work-integrated learning recruitment and employee performance. The mediation of work-integrated learning training is partial mediation, which means that without going through work-integrated learning training or going through that stage, work-integrated learning recruitment still has a significant effect on employee performance.

Keywords:- Employee Performance, Recruitment, Training, Work Integrated Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The industrial world has developed and experienced changes in the last 10 years, especially startup-based technology companies (Ferratti et al., 2021), this is in line with the development of industrial revolution 4.0 technology, which means that it also increasingly supports the development of the latest soft skills and technical skills that urgently needed by the current industrial world (Licorish et al., 2022). This has begun to be shown in the recruitment process for startup and technology companies which have problems regarding difficulties in finding suitable workforce (Chen et al., 2021), through primary data from recruitment management surveys through questionnaires which are carried out through data processing in this thesis, which conducted on startup and technology companies in March-April 2022 with 17 startup companies in Indonesia through various sizes of human resources ranging from under 50 employees to multinational startup companies consisting of more than 5,000 employees, of which there are in various business fields such as Education, Agriculture, Fisheries, Women Empowerment, E-Commerce, and Services, including these companies are Ruangguru, Schoters, to startups that take the floor on the Stock Exchange such as Nanotechnology.

Data show the results that 44% of companies stated that there were quite a lot of registrants in their company, even 13% stated that registrants were overcapacity, but there were 37% of companies stated that registrants did not comply with company specifications and 44% were in doubt about the suitability of registrants, with various factors external causes such as 40% of companies stated that this was influenced by the original quality of the educational institution and 27% were doubtful about this. can fulfill, 31% are unsure of the applicant's skills.

This is also experienced by the company PT KerabaTani Indonesia which is engaged in startups in the agricultural sector, especially in the development of agribusiness, agritech, and agricultural biotechnology. By managing 70 employees spread across several regions (KerabaTani Company Profile, 2022), this company recruits every 6 months to fill various positions, such as staff research officer for various products related to agriculture, positions needed in technology fields such as programmers, front end, back end, internet of things developers, and others. The quality of the recruitment carried out shows that the total number of applicants exceeds the company's capacity (KerabaTani Recruitment Results Information, 2022), and from the registration process many applicants still do not meet the required specifications, from the company's last 2 recruitment period data from the 40 required positions, out of 300 existing applicants, there were only 23 positions that could be fulfilled due to non-compliance with the specifications of the prospective workforce, with factors causing the positions needed to be rare and new in the world of work so that it was still difficult to be able to find suitable positions and applicants which became a separate obstacle for this company.

The company conducts a problem analysis of the causes of the high rate of applicants compared to employees who are accepted, namely the mismatch of skills possessed to the needs of the industrial world, especially the current recruitment needs, from the findings obtained, the majority of applicants come from universities located in the East Java area (Information on Recruitment Results of KerabaTani, 2021) which is the domicile of a company that has a different educational curriculum in the desired fields that are not following company needs.

Furthermore, because this startup is under the auspices of the Business and Technology Incubator of the State University of Malang which acts as a company advisor (KerabaTani Prospectus, 2021), to carry out problem-solving with business managers to look for options for recruitment methods that can

help increase the company's competitive advantage and meet recruitment needs, by looking for a recruitment method that can overcome the problem of mismatching the quality of the workforce to the recruitment needs of companies and facing the challenges of the labor market which lacks a competitive advantage in it to be able to compete. Based on this, the managers of the company collaborated on problem-solving with the business and technology incubation institution of the State University of Malang to carry out collaborative development, namely the Collaboration of the Independent Campus Program together with the Development of a work-integrated learning platform system that has been system-tested internationally, which consists of recruitment used to adjust the learning curriculum in tertiary institutions adapted to industrial needs in collaboration with a company recruitment system based on the learning outcomes of students who have used a learning curriculum that is following industry needs (Independence Campus Cooperation, State University of Malang, 2021).

Recruitment results from the work-integrated learning program between PT KerabaTani Indonesia and the State University of Malang agreed to do a training contract first for 3 months before the mid-term contract was carried out as an employee who had carried out his obligations. The recruitment results from the program begin in July 2022, by measuring employee performance in the first month after recruitment, with employee performance results requiring an increased capacity of employees recruited on several dimensions that have different needs among employees. The need for increased training for recruited employees is 45% requiring an increase in job skills, 20% requiring an increase in communication and collaboration knowledge, and 35% requiring an increase in KPI achievements with adjustments to field training (KerabaTani Monthly Report, 2022).

Based on this, to support decision-making in business, especially in the recruitment process carried out by companies and program evaluations implemented, this thesis conducts research related to the effect of implementing work-integrated learning recruitment on employee performance through the mediation variable of work-integrated learning training at PT KerabaTani Indonesia with the goal is to provide an increased perspective on the company's recruitment process, especially in the world of technology startups that require various adjustments to their needs.

II. METHODS OF RESEARCH

In this study, the type of approach used is quantitative, quantitative research is research that provides an overview with calculations and can be generalized so that it does not require in-depth data analysis because it prioritizes the dimensions of data expansion so that the results of the study are an overall picture (Kriyantono, 2020). This study uses an experimental research model, where variables will be manipulated and have an impact on other variables being tested or observed (McDaniel et al., 2001). To test the hypothesis on the existing model, this thesis carries out an experimental design, (D. Cooper & Schindler, 2003) describes the experimental method as a study of the process of

manipulating several variables to be able to affect other variables, an activity which will provide treatment to variables so that the impact on other variables can be measured.

The variables used in the research model consist of 3 variables consisting of 1 exogenous (independent) variable, 1 mediating variable, and 1 endogenous or (bound) variable. An explanation regarding these variables is that the Exogenous Variable (X) is a variable that will affect the dependent variable, both positively and negatively (Noman et al., 2021). This variable uses the notation X and the exogenous variable in this study is work-integrated learning recruitment. Next, is the Mediation Variable (Y) which is a variable that has a theoretical significance in influencing the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables to become an indirect relationship and cannot be directly measured. This variable is a variable that is between endogenous and exogenous variables so that exogenous variables do not directly influence endogenous variables (Froment & de-Besa Gutiérrez, 2022). In this study, the mediating variable used was training work-integrated learning and the Endogenous Variable (Z) is the variable that is the main target of the researcher and is the main variable that applies in the factor analysis of the research (Belloni et al., 2022). The endogenous variable used in this study is employee performance.

This study used primary data sources in field surveys with a data collection method in the form of questionnaires which were distributed to participants. Primary data is data obtained directly from first hand for analysis or finding solutions to the problems carried out (DePoy & Gitlin, 2016). This primary data was conducted utilizing a survey of the recruitment methods and work-integrated learning used by the company in the process of finding the employees needed and also a survey of performance data through the employee performance of these employees, and data on the mediating variable in the form of work-integrated learning training for employees. Other data sources used in this study are secondary data, which are data obtained from other parties such as literature, books, journals, and other sources of information that have relevance to this research, these data are used to obtain a theory that serves as the basis of the research this is to facilitate the analysis, assessment, and conclusion of the research results discussed and decision making in this study (Enghoff & Aldridge, 2019).

The population in this study were 40 employees recruited from PT KerabaTani Indonesia from educational institutions that have collaborated in terms of workforce preparation with a work-integrated learning system. Selection of employees because they are the target object of applying to the company PT KerabaTani Indonesia in the period May-June 2022, this prospective workforce was chosen because it is a direct target of work-integrated learning research. The selection of these participants used the census method, which is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples (Martínez-Mesa et al., 2016). The analysis technique that can answer this research is testing the validity, reliability and followed by Partial Least Square (PLS) to test the effect between variables and test mediation.

III. FINDING AND DISUSSION

❖ Findings

In the process of giving answers from respondents to research variables, this answer uses a Likert scale from a score of 1 to 5 and the average results of variables with predetermined categories, with the following categories:

$$\text{class intervals} = \frac{\text{Highest score} - \text{lowest score}}{\text{Number of classes}} = \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,80$$

Based on these categories, the highest score is 5 and the lowest is 1. From this formula, a class interval of 0.80 is obtained with a distance per category. From this, the provisions for the assessment category are as follows:

Table 1. Assessment Category

Interval	Category	Description
1,00 - 1,80	1	Very low
1,81 - 2,60	2	Low
2,61 - 3,40	3	Enough
3,41 - 4,20	4	High
4,21 - 5,00	5	Very High

➤ Work Integrated Learning Recruitment Description

The description of the respondents' answers to the work integrated learning recruitment variable the respondent's answer to the work-integrated learning recruitment variable is 4.48, which means it is classified as high, meaning that the application of work-integrated learning recruitment has been able to explain how the capabilities of the workforce recruited can match industry needs.

In the educational institution dimension, the respondents' ratings reached an average of 4.38, which means that the application to educational institutions in terms of the workforce recruited from work-integrated learning has a relatively high score, with the highest score by X.1.II with the dimension that works recruitment Integrated learning has the impression of attracting the interest of prospective workers to prepare themselves for the world of work.

On the Student dimension, the dimension of getting scores is in the high category, namely work integrated learning recruitment, with the high category at 4.48. In the industrial world dimension, it achieved a high average in the dimension of work-integrated learning implementation and recruitment with a score of 4.58 which stated that the industrial world could adjust to the implementation of work-integrated learning recruitment in absorbing labor and could match organizational and industry needs. With a high average, it means that the recruitment of work-integrated learning within the scope of the industrial world has obtained a suitability that can be applied.

➤ Description of Work Integrated Learning Training

The following is an explanation of the respondents' answers regarding the training variables applied to the work integrated learning training process all dimensions get scores

in the high category, which means that the training is carried out according to the needs and work-integrated learning training methods. This suitability is obtained from the total average rating reaching 4.58 in the high category, this suitability is also emphasized by dividing the discussion of per dimensional data.

The practicum training dimension gets scores in the high category through simulation assessments and practicum training courses in its implementation and gets a score of 4.50 in the high category. The second dimension is the Internship, with the full performance of expert supervision from practitioners according to the needs of the job, and getting a score of 4.575 with a high-value category. The second dimension with high value ensures how the workforce gets regulations and training per the directions of practitioners and field supervisors.

In the dimension of cooperative education in integrated learning work training, there is a high score of 4.775. This is because learning is still integrating the world of work with separate theoretical training in several stages, but still getting good results following the training objectives to improve theoretical education and better practical collaboration on other instruments. In the field education dimension, the criteria for a high score were achieved by achieving a score of 4.45 which means that the training process is also based on field needs which are interpreted in the form of training and habituation.

➤ Description of Employee Performance

A description of the respondents' answers to the employee performance variable the average total answers concerning the employee performance assessment instrument reach a value of 4.62 in the high category. This means that the employee performance given in the industry in terms of performance achievement has a high compatibility with the suitability of the capabilities that have been prepared by the workforce from the recruitment process.

In this variable, 3 dimensions are measured, namely task performance with an average of 4.18 with dimensions of work assessment according to quantity and quality. In the contextual performance assessment dimension, the assessment gets a value of 4.825 with the approved category through the outstanding progress performance assessment of the existing work. In the adaptive performance assessment dimension, this dimension scores 4.85 in the approved category, through the ability of employees to adapt to the company in the future and according to the needs of the industrial world.

➤ Hypothesis test

The next step in testing the hypothesis is to estimate the path coefficient which is evaluated based on the T-Statistic value. These estimates can display values that show the relationship to latent variables in the bootstrapping procedure. Items measured with a statistical significance of a T-value greater than 1.96 and a p-value of less than 0.05 at a significance of 0.05 (5%). While the parameter coefficients show the direction of the original sample's positive and negative influences and the magnitude of the influence of the

independent variable on the dependent. The following is the path coefficient to be able to see the T-Statistic.

Table 5. Path Coefficients

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Recruitment Work Integrated Learning → Training Work Integrated Learning	0,432	3,601	0,000
Recruitment Work Integrated Learning → Employee Performance	0,337	3,037	0,003
Training Work Integrated Learning → Employee Performance	0,505	4,098	0,000
Recruitment Work Integrated Learning → Training Work Integrated Learning → Employee Performance	0,218	2,585	0,010

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

Based on the results of the path coefficient test in the table, can be used to prove the hypothesis in the following research:

- The effect of work-integrated learning recruitment on work-integrated learning training, in the table it can be seen that recruitment with work-integrated learning has a positive and significant effect on work-integrated learning training with a parameter coefficient value of 0.432. This can be seen from the T-statistics of $3.601 > 1.96$ and a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that work-integrated learning recruitment influences work-integrated learning training in this study sample so H1 states that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on work-integrated learning training so the hypothesis is accepted;
- The effect of work-integrated learning recruitment on employee performance, in the table above it, is known that the effect is positive and significant because the resulting parameter value reaches 0.337 and this can be seen from the path coefficient which shows a T-statistic value of $3.037 > 1.96$ and a p-value -value $0.003 < 0.05$. Based on these statistics it can be concluded that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance in this study so that H2 which states work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance can be accepted;
- Effect of work-integrated learning training on employee performance. At this stage, it is known that work-integrated learning training has a positive effect on employee performance, with a parameter coefficient value of 0.505. This can be seen from the path coefficient with a T-statistic value of $4.098 > 1.96$ and a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these calculations, it can be concluded that integrated learning training work for the key performance indicators as stated in H3 of this study, which has a positive and significant effect, can be accepted and supported.
- The effect of work-integrated learning recruitment on employee performance by mediating work-integrated learning training. The table shows that work-integrated learning training can mediate positively and significantly the relationship between work-integrated learning recruitment and employee performance. This can be seen from the acquisition of the parameter coefficient values which reach 0.218. In addition, the significant effect can be seen from the T-statistic value of $2.585 > 1.96$ and the p-value of $0.010 < 0.05$. Based on this statistically, it can be concluded that work-integrated learning training can

significantly mediate the relationship between work-integrated learning recruitment and employee performance in this study sample, so H4 which states that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance, by mediating work training integrated learning accepted.

❖ Discussion

➤ Effect of work integrated learning recruitment on work integrated learning training

The findings of this study are known after the data is processed using the help of SmarPLS3 software and these findings can be revealed that work-integrated learning recruitment is proven to have a significant effect on work-integrated learning training. This means that the recruitment method can properly support the training process per the needs of the industry by paying special attention to employees so that they can achieve competency compatibility with the industrial world. Thus, the hypothesis states that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on work-integrated learning training is accepted, meaning that the higher the quality of work-integrated learning recruitment can affect the level of quality of work-integrated learning training the better the employees.

The results of this study are in line with some of the results of previous studies such as; (Sinaga & Nawangsari, 2019) who reported that recruitment is an important factor in improving training that suits industry needs and integrates creative insight, perseverance, and sensitivity in employees which in turn can drive changes in management innovation related to practices and processes according to world needs industry. On the other hand, (Anwar & Abdullah, n.d.) revealed that a good recruitment system and better quality tend to able to display innovative work behavior, such as; the formation of ideas, promotion of ideas, and realization of ideas, both for self-development and to develop the potential of their subordinates and can also influence creativity and innovation according to the needs of the industrial world.

➤ Effect of work integrated learning recruitment on employee performance

The findings of this study are known after the data is processed using the help of SmarPLS3 software and these findings can be revealed that work-integrated learning recruitment is proven to have a significant effect on employee

performance. This means that the high quality of recruitment provided by the company to its subordinates by paying special attention to achieving the best performance affects employee performance. Thus, the hypothesis states that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance is accepted, meaning that the better the quality of the recruitment provided and the ability to inspire subordinates, the better the level of employee performance can be.

This study is in line with several study results that have been reported by (Arifin et al., 2020) which reveal that an employee with good recruitment qualities will increase appropriate performance capabilities and be able to overcome various problems that exist in the world of work. On the one hand, recruitment according to the needs of the industrial world can affect the quality of employee performance on performance measures (Pavláková Dočekalová et al., 2018). Thus, work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance.

➤ *Effect of work integrated learning training on employee performance.*

The findings of this study are known after the data is processed using the SmartPLS3 software and these findings can be revealed that work-integrated learning training is proven to have a significant effect on employee performance. This means that a high level of quality training for an employee to be creative and actively involved in processes that can lead to creative results can affect employee performance. Thus, the hypothesis that states that work-integrated learning training has a significant effect on employee performance is accepted, meaning that the better the company is at implementing work-integrated learning training, the better employee performance levels can be affected.

In addition, employees with good levels of employee performance tend to have high motivation to innovate and always try to influence their co-workers to be able to develop new ideas and methods that are better than before. This study is relevant to the results of previous studies such as; (Haryono et al., 2020) who reported that training has been considered an important pioneer of innovation and an important component for the sustainability of the organization itself which has a direct effect on employee performance. In addition, according to (Alhempri et al., 2021) innovative work behavior does not only describe the problem of how to generate ideas, but also the behavior required for the implementation of these ideas which can improve individual and organizational performance which has a direct impact on work accuracy and problem-solving, communication, and teamwork as well as adjustments to company changes. Not only that, but someone who has received good training according to (Karatzas et al., 2020) can increase employee creativity by providing psychological conditions, which encourage employee motivation to continue learning.

➤ *Effect of work integrated learning recruitment on employee performance by mediating work integrated learning training*

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, shows that work-integrated learning training can mediate the relationship

between work-integrated learning recruitment and employee performance, thus the hypothesis states that work-integrated learning recruitment has a significant effect on employee performance by mediating work-integrated learning training is supported (accepted). The mediation nature of work-integrated learning training in these findings is partial mediation, which means that without going through work-integrated learning training or whether this variable exists or not, work-integrated learning recruitment still has a significant effect on employee performance.

Based on the respondent's answers, the results of this study report that companies that can give responsibility to employees to complete their work properly through a recruitment system integrated with the world of education, and can provide the attention that has an effect on increasing employee performance in the form of training according to needs through training work integrated learning, in improving skills and can also help in seeing things in a new way that are difficult to understand at first, making it easier, and being able to provide direct guidance when employees have problems at work. Some of these things can affect work-integrated learning training, in this case, work-integrated learning training is marked by the results of training for employees by encouraging employees to adjust to company updates, the level of accuracy of work, and also employees' perceptions of the results of their training that they get with this approach. new and different in solving a problem, this is also the result of the support of the recruitment and mediation process by the integrated learning work training method. All of this, in turn, affects the recruitment of work-integrated learning where employees are able and encouraged to develop the skills needed by the industrial world through the pre-recruitment, selection stage, the training stage. These findings are in line with the results of a study conducted by (Suwanto & Subyantoro, 2019) which revealed that work-integrated learning recruitment can be associated with craft and creative work results, which in turn can increase innovative work behavior and have a good effect on employee performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion described in the previous chapter, the results of this study conclude that work-integrated learning recruitment can have a significant influence on work-integrated learning training for employees of PT KerabaTani Indonesia; Recruitment of work integrated learning can have a significant influence on the employee performance of employees of PT KerabaTani Indonesia; Work integrated learning training can have a significant impact on employee performance for employees of PT KerabaTani Indonesia; and Work integrated learning training can significantly mediate the effect of work integrated learning recruitment on employee performance of employees of PT KerabaTani Indonesia.

Based on the results and conclusions above, the suggestions that can be given in this study are for PT KerabaTani Indonesia; It is known that the recruitment of work-integrated learning is an important factor in improving employee performance, so the management of PT KerabaTani

Indonesia needs to increase returns related to the company's ability to inspire and provide an overview of existing career opportunities, and increase attention to employees who influence their performance improvement, and the company also needs to be a good listener for all employees to improve work behavior.

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